

Detailed Guidelines and Future Scope of Improvement

1. The rationale for using Dempster Shafer theory to assess collective confidence:

Our objective is to measure the quality of the training data by analyzing how the factors that can introduce uncertainty in the data have been handled while collecting and processing the data. While data experts can provide the judgment about such quality claims regarding the data, we suggest involving various experts (with diverse expertise) to provide their opinion about the quality of the data by judging the evidences of the quality claims. However, to reduce the impact of the subjective nature of this task we decided to quantify the experts' judgment in terms of Collective Confidence. We emphasize here that we are not only focusing on the confidence of the experts in the collected evidence about the good or bad quality of the data but also the lack of confidence due to epistemic uncertainty of the evidences. Therefore, we argue that Dempster Shafer's theory of evidence is a good fit for this purpose as this theory not only considers the probability of one event at a time (good or bad) but also the chances of either of them if concrete evidence is missing. In other words, we are not only measuring the data uncertainty but also the uncertainty in the experts' individual beliefs about the data quality and finally combining them to deduce the collective confidence.

2. Elicitation of the source of uncertainty and corresponding addressing criteria:

The process of eliciting the sources of uncertainty and the corresponding addressing criteria greatly varies based on the data type and the problem domain. Following are the questions that we tried to answer while eliciting the sources and addressing criteria of uncertainty.

Q1. What are the major concerns regarding the ML problem, application domain & data type? (Whether the data correctly represents the problem or not, properly processed or not, the data source is reliable or not, training data covers the critical cases or not, data is unbiased or not, etc.)

Q2. What factors play important roles to cause those uncertainties? (In the example given in the paper, environmental variability, spatial variability, pedestrians types variability are important factors for the data to be representative. Similarly, for other sources of uncertainty find the key factors)

Q3. What can be done to control those factors in order to minimize the scope of uncertainty? (How much variability should be addressed by the data assuming that it is not possible to cover all kinds of diversity. Similarly, what kind of preprocessing is necessary to be in accordance with the ML problem at hand, etc.)

3. Key guidelines to collect and assess the pieces of evidence:

After collecting the data, early exploratory data analysis (EDA) can be done based on the type of application domain and the data. The procedure to perform an EDA is subjective and the quality of the outcome greatly depends on the expertise and knowledge of the experts involved in the process. However, we can give some key guidelines that can help to follow our proposed method to achieve the expected outcome. EDA on image data is very different than on tabular data.

In the case of tabular data, the following are the example key points to look for while performing EDA:

- a. Correlations among the features.
 - b. Range and distribution of the features’ value
 - c. Histograms based on the features to find any hidden bias of the data
 - d. Outliers or anomalies that need to be discarded
- Etc.

In the case of video/image data, we mainly focused on two aspects, such as diversity and annotation properties. To avoid any bias of the authors of this paper, we referred to the original papers about both the datasets and thoroughly scrutinized the data analysis done by the respective data experts. All our findings listed in the paper can be directly found on the cited papers. Our general suggestions to find evidences on the image data are as follows:

- a. Check the data source: compatibility of the camera with the application domain, image quality, frame rate etc.
- b. Check the collection diversity: What environmental factors (e.g. place, weather, brightness, etc.) have been covered during the collection phase.
- c. Check the annotation protocol: Bounding box aspect ratio, occlusion ratio, markups for necessary attributes, etc.
- d. Labeling and class distribution
- e. Key features distributions: Height, occluded areas, etc.

Upon collecting such evidences we evaluated them from ML perspective and also from a domain perspective. In the future, to prove the generalizability of the proposed method, we plan to apply our method in another domain where we can involve domain experts to reassess our findings.

The findings of the CLATECH dataset are already included in the paper. Following is the list of evidences collected from the JAAD dataset.

Criteria	Evidence ID	Evidences collected by data experts	Weight	Assessment of evidence	
				By ML Expert	Domain Expert
CID-1	EV-1	Data is collected in various weather conditions, like cloudy, clear, rainy, etc.	3	Positive	Positive
CID-2	EV-2	Data is collected mostly in the daytime except for a few night videos.	3	Negative	Negative
CID-3	EV-3	Moderately crowded areas are covered.	1	Positive	Positive
CID-4	EV-4	Data is collected in multiple cities.	3	Positive	Positive
CID-5	EV-5	Specific ranges of pixels for near or far pedestrians are not determined.	2	Cannot say	Cannot say
CID-6	EV-6	Different poses are marked (walking, standing, etc.)	2	Positive	Positive
CID-7	EV-7	Various accessories are marked.	2	Positive	Positive
CID-8	EV-8	Partial occlusion (25%-75%) and heavy occlusion (more than 75%)	3	Positive	Positive
CID-9	EV-9	Based on age and sex various types of pedestrians are marked.	3	Positive	Positive
CID-10	EV-10	Several rare cases are covered are marked for testing. Such as heavy	3	Positive	Positive

		occlusion due to accessories, small height (kid).			
CID-11	EV-11	Video is collected by the dataset creator (not the third party), no data corruption is reported.	3	Positive	Positive
CID-12	EV-12	Data is labeled as ‘pedestrian’, ‘ped’, and ‘people’ for the individual with behavioral tags, bystanders, and groups of people respectively.	3	Positive	Positive
CID-13	EV-13	Annotation protocol is not clear.	2	Cannot say	Cannot say

4. Detailed Calculation:

The calculation for both datasets can be found in the excel file named “**Detailed Calculation.xlsx**” added to this replication package.

5. Future scope of improvement (Multiple experts and their credibility factors):

Although we run through the example in the paper from the perspectives of two experts only, for simplicity, it is quite possible that in a real-world scenario more than two experts need to be involved to judge the data quality from various perspectives. Each of their judgments needs to be combined in a computationally inexpensive way. Furthermore, there should be a provision to update the already combined and calculated collective confidence if a new expert (new belief structure) needs to be brought in. Moreover, more experts means more chances of disagreement. Unlike the traditional DS combination rule that does not give intuitive results in case of conflicts, Yager’s rule does not ignore the conflicts and adjusts the combined belief accordingly. Therefore, we use Yager’s rule of combination instead of the classical DS rule of combination. Following is the formula that shows that it is possible to include as many experts’ opinions as possible using this rule.

Suppose, there are ***n* belief structures (*n* experts)** m_1, m_2, \dots, m_n and A_i is an element of the set of the focal elements associated with i^{th} belief structure m_i . The combined ground probability of A is defined as:

$$q(A) = \sum_{\cap_{i=1}^n A_i=A} m_1(A_1)m_2(A_2) \dots m_n(A_n)$$

It is even possible to introduce credibility factors for each source of belief structures (in other words for each expert) following the Dempster Shafer framework. In a scenario where multiple experts are asked to provide their opinion and some of the experts are of great importance due to their area of expertise, then it is important to assign credibility factor to each of the experts while combining their belief structures. Belief mass (m) can be adjusted based on the **credibility factor** (α) assigned to it as shown below:

$$m(A)_{adjusted} = m(A) * \alpha + \frac{1-\alpha}{n}$$

Here, n is the number of elements in the frame of discernment.

The detailed calculation of the same is under the scope of our future work.

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